

Effect of Parent Participation on Youngsters' Schooling at Primary Level

Namra Munir¹, Rashid Minas Wattoo², Muhammad Asif Shahzad³

Abstract

Children of educated parents are more likely to do well in school if they attend a good school with a good teacher. In most cases, a child's chances of doing well in life improve if they come from a family where at least one parent has a college degree. It stands to reason that children of high-income and high-education parents will do well academically. Parental involvement in their children's education extends beyond the classroom and into the home. Parents often offer their children reading materials such as books, newspapers, and academic publications. The education level of a person's parents significantly affects the education level of that person's children. A survey of Vehari district residents was conducted as part of the study. Finding out if and how student performance improves with parental involvement is the primary focus of this research. Primary school educators in the Vehari district were the subjects of this research. The 300 educators in the Vehari region were randomly chosen for this investigation. The data was compiled using a carefully crafted and field-tested questionnaire. The grading method was set up as a five-point Likert scale with five possible locations for each answer. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined to be 0.712. The study's objective explored whether parental involvement in their children's education improves their academic performance.

Keywords: parent's participation, student's accomplishment, inspirations

1. Introduction

The involvement of parents in their children's education refers to the time and effort put in by parents outside of school hours. Parents' involvement in their kids' lives is crucial to their academic and social growth (Ali and Saleh, 2022). Some benefits of parents being involved in their children's schools are better academic performance, more cooperative social behavior, more money, and chances to talk to each other one-on-one. Allen (2008) found that many parents took pictures of their kids on their first day of school and may have even followed the bus to make sure their kids got there safely. Parents' participation in their kids' classroom activities is crucial. Parental involvement has been on the rise recently, and studies have found that it positively affects their children's school performance and attendance (Lewis, 2008; Trusty, Mellin, and Herbert, 2008).

Over the past several decades, several researchers have spent considerable time examining the connection between parental involvement and students' academic success. Most people think a student's chances of doing well in school increase with how much her mother is involved in her life. However, many factors, including the parent's relationship with the teacher, the size of the school, the type of school (public vs. private), the student's grade, the student's uniqueness, and the student's sexual orientation, have been identified as having an impact on the level of parental involvement.

There is a positive correlation between parents' involvement in their children's education and their socioeconomic status, as suggested by Yens and Jament (2008). Sanders and Sheldon (2009) found that parents who were actively involved in their children's education at home and school saw significant gains in their student's academic performance. According to Smits and Hosgor's (2006) research, students' enthusiasm for social studies increases when their parents are actively involved in their education. Since every child undergoes the same stages of development and has the same rights, parental involvement in their children's education is crucial in every society. The time and energy put in by parents are invaluable to their children's development and future success. Parental inclusion happens when parents are interested in school activities or events and when teachers give parents learning materials or information about their child's grades. Teachers who prioritize parental involvement often notice major shifts in their classrooms. The greater the involvement of the custodians, the greater the positive reinforcement, behavior, and academic performance of the entire class.

Maternal connotation and dedication to education are presently more related than ever because it is in degeneration. Educators believe that their interactions with students' guardians have declined since 2016. Protectors communicate with teachers and students through remote means, such as student portals. They are also still less likely to attend parent-teacher meetings or school activities. The change is shocking and worries because of what it means for moms' sense of security. While modern technology has made it easier for families to stay in touch, students still need to catch up when their parents need to give them the time and attention they need.

Researchers in education looked at fifty studies and found a link between family involvement and academic success. Moreover, teachers can raise students' achievement by encouraging early parental involvement (Shahzad et al., 2022; Bibi & Ali, 2021). Student success and future confidence introductions are built on the firm foundation of maternal associations shaped during the elementary school years.

Drenching mothers also helps cut down on "continuing absence," or being absent for more than 20 days of the school year. Students learning gaps narrow by about 20 percentage points when parents actively participate in

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Education University of Education, Lahore – Vehari Campus, Pakistan

²Assistant Professor, Department of Education University of Sialkot, Sialkot, Pakistan

³Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Education, Lahore – Vehari Campus, Pakistan

their children's education, such as through home-based appointments with teachers. Students who need to meet grade expectations and their parents who are connected to them report shorter periods wasted in class, even after considering representative mark levels and historical absences. Parent-teacher dialogue encourages students to participate in class actions and boosts overall engagement.

This study set out to look into how much of an impact parental involvement has on a young child's primary school education. Having this information about parents' influences on their children's education was a priority for the study's authors. The research aims to determine if students with more involved parents performed better in school and exhibited better social behavior. Classroom problems experienced by students will be mitigated. This research shows us that there are countless ways in which parental involvement affects children's academic success.

This research is related to the effect of parent's participation on youngster's schooling. This research study is designed to explore participation of guardians and its impact on the youngster's scholastic accomplishment. This study is helpful for the parents because parents will be more conscious of necessity of their contribution in their youngster's schooling. This research study highlights the significance of parents-teachers collaboration also promotes a solid joint accountability for youngster's success. Future scholars in the field of parental connection and its impact on scholastic success will benefit from this research. This research also serves as a foundation for future research. Finally, this research also aids in the development of a sense of community and collegiality among parents and educators in general.

2. Review of Related Literature

According to Colombo, Hogue, Faw and Liddle (2006), parents' involvement in education, broadly construed to include a variety of spheres and practices related to child-rearing, focuses to a surprisingly large extent on incorporating homework. Parents' involvement in their children's homework reinforces the positive associations between parental involvement and students' attitudes toward homework and schoolwork, self-observations, and effective work habits and self-control. Even so, studies on how homework affects how well students do in school often fail to show positive results. Research shows no correlation between the amount of time parents spend on homework and their children's academic performance. For three days, a homework journal recorded how much time parents spent monitoring and adjusting their children's homework daily. The data used in this analysis were derived from the median value of the first two days of journal entries due to the high frequency of missing data on the third day of data collection. The journal contained data on the amount of work each student put into their assignments.

The environment a child grows up in, both at home and in the broader community, significantly impacts their development and growth (Pelletier, & Brent, 2002; Senturk & Ali, 2021; Sajid & Ali, 2018; Ashraf & Ali, 2018). Most of a child's first social interactions and exposure to cultural norms happen with their family. Children gain a sense of self and family through relationships with their parents, siblings, and extended family. There are more people in a child's life, including peers, teachers, and other adults, in the community, who can all contribute to their growth and development. In the community, children can explore, learn, and grow. They may be exposed to different ideas, cultural activities, and ways of expressing themselves. They may also be exposed to different types of people and their perspectives, which can help to shape their attitudes and values. Children can learn, grow, and explore in family and community settings that are safe and helpful.

School readiness is the ability of a child to start and succeed in school. Parents have a big part to play in ensuring their kids have the skills and knowledge they need to do well in school (Rogers, Theule, Ryan, Adams and Keating, 1999). Parents can help their children become school-ready by providing them with a safe and stimulating home environment, such as by reading to them, talking with them, and encouraging them to explore their environment. Parents can also prepare their kids for school by teaching them how to count, recognize letters, and solve problems. Children can learn the social, emotional, and academic skills they need to do well in school if they have access to good childcare and preschool programs. Parents can also help their kids by having high expectations for them, giving them positive feedback, and talking to their teachers often.

Higher parental involvement in their children's schooling has been associated with tremendous academic success (Barnard, 2004). It has been shown that when parents are involved in their children's education, their kids do better in school and are more likely to graduate. Attending school events, assisting with homework, and communicating with teachers are all examples of how parents can get involved in their children's education. Parents can also help their children emotionally by taking an interest in and encouraging their efforts in school. Studies have shown that when parents are involved in their children's schooling, the children flourish in terms of both self-esteem and social competence.

When looking at aspects of a person's life that have to do with their family, their educational level is crucial. "Education is the most important factor in determining social and economic growth around the world" (UNESCO, 2013). People with a good education are better able to take advantage of opportunities and help society. A person's social and economic status can improve with more education. Family ties tend to have more weight for those with less formal schooling. A child's success in school is correlated with their parents' and caregivers' ability to provide a nurturing home life and expose them to high-quality education (Cacioppo, Hughes, Waite, Hawkey & Thisted, 2006). It is probably because kids from educated households are more likely to be exposed to positive influences

that help them succeed in school. Those with more education, however, still value the support they can get from their families. Those with advanced degrees benefit even more from them. The National Bureau of Economic Research (Braybrooke, 2014) found that the level of education is directly related to income. Having a degree opens up more employment opportunities and increases earning potential. Therefore, people of varying educational backgrounds can benefit from family-based interventions. It is possible to make some broad statements about the relationship between parents and society, however, including the following:

- parental involvement is generally viewed favorably and is a force for good in society;
- parental involvement is often considered a social responsibility;
- Parental involvement is a source of support for children.

The proper role of parents in society and the advantages they can provide to their children is a hotly contested topic. The research community is split on whether parental involvement should be encouraged, limited, or eliminated.

Research has repeatedly shown (Englund, Luckner, Whaley, & Egeland, 2004) that parental involvement, both at home and at school, is linked to student academic success, school engagement, and school adjustment. However, one of the most significant obstacles for teachers is getting parents involved, especially those from low-income areas (Smalley & Reyes-Blanes, 2001). Lack of financial or other resources may make it harder for parents to support their children's academic success. Research has shown that parents who are more interested in their children's lives tend to be from higher socioeconomic backgrounds and have more education than those who are less involved (e.g., Englund et al., 2004; Feliciano, 2006). Minke and Anderson (2005) say that working- and lower-class parents have it more complicated than middle-class parents regarding their children's educational opportunities.

It has been established that low-income adolescents are at a heightened risk for academic difficulties due partly to the lack of financial and material resources available to their homes and schools (Kozol, 2005). In the context of this study, the term "inner-city school" refers to a certain kind of secondary school in a city. Public schools in urban cores typically cater to low-income kids of colour, in contrast to the private schools and white pupils found in the suburbs (Brunetti, 2006). So, many families in inner cities are poor and have to deal with the dangers of living in areas with high crime, high unemployment, gang activity, illegal drug trade, and constant violence (Zhou, 2003). In addition, high school students in urban regions are more likely to drop out and exhibit poor behaviour in class than their suburban and rural counterparts (Bemak, Chung, & Siroskey-Sabdo, 2005).

Parental involvement, especially from a mother's point of view, is commonly held to have a bearing on children's academic success. It is multidimensional and bidirectional and has been displayed to take clear associations along with communal and scholarly results for youngsters. Customarily, maternal attachment has been considered in place of engaging protectors in school-based training, and junctures have been recognized with their toddler's tutoring. Once custodians remain engaged with their kid's institute lives, pupils take the home-based assistance and info they need to finish the tasks, encouraging a deep-rooted love of learning.

Rogala, Silvern, Brabham and Ross (2001) assessed that parental participation and the desire for prior accomplishment are vital to look at these elements from the get-go in kids' lives. A few specialists have recommended that parental relationships and parental desires may affect more youthful youngsters' accomplishments compared to those of kids in the later years of primary school through secondary school. Furthermore, early encounters with guardians in critical thinking circumstances before the school day may be important in later scholastic accomplishment. Early experiences could be especially important if parents put their kids in situations that require them to think critically. It could prepare them for later learning and help them develop early flexible skills, like finding resources to help them solve problems. Because of these possible effects, it is important to find out how the different parts of a child's education affect each other.

3. Research Methodology

Descriptive research is a method used to describe the findings of a study. This method aims to discover underlying structures and associations in the data. Data visualization tools like graphs, charts, and tables can be derived from descriptive research. The population of the study consisted on primary school teachers in district Vehari. The research collected the sample of 300 primary school teachers to derive the results for study. A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. The present study was aimed to analyze effect of parent participation on youngsters' schooling at primary level in Vehari district. Data is composed through well design and pre-testing questionnaire.

4. Data Analysis

Table 1 displays the teacher's qualifications. Most respondents (137) were now studying in master's programs, which is 45.7%. One hundred eight respondents are currently studying in BA, which is 36.0%, and 55 are currently studying in FA, which is 18.3% out of 300 total respondents. Similarly, the result is a mean value of 2.27 and a standard deviation of 0.753.

Table 1: Respondents Qualification

Option	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
FA	55	18.3	2.27	.753
BA	108	36.0		
MA	137	45.7		

Figure 1: Respondents Qualification

Table 2: Good home environment has positive influence on children’s learning

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	SD
Strongly Agree	52.3	4.52	.507
Agree	47.3		
Undecided	0.3		
Disagree	--		
Strongly Disagree	--		

Table 2 shows that 99.6% of teachers agreed that a good home environment positively influences children’s learning. In comparison, 0.3% of respondents remained neutral in their responses. In the same way, the cumulative result is that the mean value is 4.52, and the standard deviation value is 0.507. Thus, it is concluded after data analysis that good home environment has optimistic effect on youngsters’ learning.

Figure 2: Good home environment has optimistic impact on youngsters’ learning

Table 3 shows that 99.7% of teachers agreed with the statement that parents' participation in educational happenings affects their offspring's performance. 0.3% remained neutral in their response. In the same way, the cumulative result is a mean value of 4.53 and a standard deviation value of 0.519. Thus, it is concluded after data analysis that parents' participation in educational happenings positively affects their offspring's performance.

Table 3: The contribution of parents in instructional activities are affect their children performance

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	SD
Strongly Agree	53.7	4.53	.519
Agree	46		
Undecided	.3		
Disagree	--		
Strongly disagree	--		

Figure 3: The participation of parents in educational activities are affect their children performance**Table 4: Parent's contribution has favorable effect on children success**

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
Strongly Agree	57.3	4.55	.549
Agree	40.7		
Undecided	1.7		
Disagree	.3		
Strongly Disagree	00		

Table 4 shows that 98% of teachers agreed that parents' contributions positively affect children's success. 3% of respondents disagreed, and 1.7% remained neutral in their responses. In the same way, the cumulative result is that the mean value is 4.55, and the standard deviation value is 0.549. Thus, it is determined later in the data analysis that parents' contributions favor children's success.

Figure 4: Parents contribution has favorable effect on children success

Table 5 shows that 100% of respondents agreed that parent participation benefits their children's abilities. So, the cumulative result is a mean value of 4.74 and a standard deviation of 0.438. After looking at the data, it is clear that parents' involvement is very good for their children's skills.

Table 5: Parent’s participation is extremely beneficial to their children’s abilities

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	SD
Strongly Agree	74.3		
Agree	25.7		
Undecided	--	4.74	0.438
Disagree	--		
Strongly disagree	--		

Figure 5: Parent’s participation is extremely beneficial to their children’s abilities

Table 6: Parent’s participation provides clear information regarding their children’s careers

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	SD
Strongly Agree	51		
Agree	48		
Undecided	1	4.47	.519
Disagree	--		
Strongly Disagree	--		

Table 6 shows that 99% of teachers agreed that parent participation provides clear information regarding their children's careers, while 1% responded neutrally. In the same way, the cumulative result is a mean value of 4.47 and a standard deviation of 0.519. So, after looking at the data, it has been decided that parents' involvement gives them clear information about their children's careers.

Figure 6: Parent’s participation provides clear information regarding their children’s careers

Table 7 shows that 98% of teachers agreed that parents' contribution to their children's education is critical, while 2% responded neutrally. Similarly, the cumulative result is a mean of 4.51 and a standard deviation of .539. Thus, it is concluded after data analysis that parents' contribution to their children's education is critical.

Table 7: Contribution of parents in their youngsters' education is critical

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	SD
Strongly Agree	52.7		
Agree	45.3		
Undecided	2	4.51	.539
Disagree	00		
Strongly Disagree	00		

Figure 7: Contribution of parents in their youngsters' education is critical**Table 8: Parents give supplementary reading materials to their kid's**

Option	Percentage	Mean Score	SD
Strongly Agree	51.7		
Agree	48.3		
Undecided	--	4.52	.501
Disagree	--		
Strongly Disagree	--		

Table 8 shows that 100% of teachers agreed that parents give supplementary reading materials to their kids. In the same way, the cumulative result is a mean value of 4.52 and a standard deviation of 0.501. So, after looking at the data, we can say that parents give their children extra books to read.

Figure 8: Parents give supplementary reading materials to their kid's

5. Findings

On the basis of results the following findings/results have been perceived:

- i. 99.6% teachers were agreed that a good home environment has a favorable influence on youngsters' learning while .3% remained neutral in their response. In the same way cumulative result is mean value is 4.52 and Standard Deviation value is .507.

- ii. 99.7% teachers were agreed that parents' participation in educational activities has an influence on their youngsters' performance while .3% remained neutral in their response. In the same way cumulative result is mean value is 4.53 and Standard Deviation value is .519 (Table 4.3).
- iii. 98% teachers were agreed that the input of parents has a favorable effect on the success of their offspring while 1.7% remained neutral and .3% were disagreed in their response. In the same way cumulative result is mean value is 4.55 and Standard Deviation value is .549 (Table 4.4).
- iv. 100% respondents were agreed that parental participation is extremely beneficial to their youngsters' talents. So, the cumulative result is mean value that is 4.74 and Standard Deviation value is .438 (Table 4.5).
- v. 99% teachers were agreed that parent's participation provides clear information regarding their children's careers while 1% are neutral in their response. In the same way cumulative result is mean value is 4.47 and Standard Deviation value is .519 (Table 4.6).
- vi. 98% teachers were agreed that parent's participation is vital in children's learning while 2% remained neutral in their response. In the same way cumulative result is mean value is 4.51 and Standard Deviation value is .539 (Table 4.7).
- vii. 100% teachers were agreed that parents should give supplementary reading materials for their youngster's. In the same way cumulative result is mean value is 4.52 and Standard Deviation value is .501 (Table 4.8).

6. Conclusions

On the basis of data analysis, the resulting conclusions were made: The study concluded that Children's education depends on their parents. Parents who help their kids with school create a good learning environment and help them do better in school. Parents can be involved in school by attending school events, helping out in the classroom, helping with homework, and attending parent-teacher conferences. When parents help their kids with school, their grades, test scores, attendance, social skills, and self-esteem improve. Support and advice from parents can also help kids understand school. Parents may help their children succeed in school by being involved. The study also concluded that a positive home environment influences children's learning. Participation of parents in educational activities has a beneficial impact on their children's performance. Parent's contribution has constructive impact on their children's achievement. Parental participation is very beneficial to their children's talents. Parent's participation provides clear information regarding their children's careers. Parent's participation is critical to children's learning. So, the study finally also concluded that parents give their children supplementary reading material.

6.1. Recommendations

They work together by giving their kids money for pocket money, helping them with their homework, taking them to educational events, and not fighting in front of them. The parents may provide their children with enough time to show academic achievement in school. Parents may offer a decent school, home tuition, sports, and library trips.

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